

ELENE MOBILE APP DOWNLOAD AND USAGE STATISTICS

ELDERS LEARNING ENGLISH FOR EUROPE
2021-1-PL01-KA220-ADU-000033465

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Introduction

The ELENE application is an innovative tool for learning English based on the "situational learning" methodology. Its features, such as memory/flash cards, AI videos from the ELENE YouTube channel, and quizzes, create a comprehensive educational platform. The application is distinguished by the personalization of the user's experience, which is reflected in the adaptation of lessons and menus to the language version selected by the user and an individual progress ranking.

Innovative technologies

ELENE is distinguished by the use of advanced technologies such as text-to-speech in memory cards, which facilitates learning pronunciation, displaying videos with dialogues, personal progress ranking and one-touch translation. These technologies not only facilitate learning, but also contribute to the creation of interactive and engaging educational content.

Application welcome page

The application welcome page is the user's first point of contact with ELENE. The project logo and the logos of the project partners can be found here. The user also has the option of translating the application content into his or her native language, making access to education even more open and accessible. There is only 6 languages supported including English.

Privacy policy in English

20:10 Co-funded by the European Union **SITUATED ENGLISH** Study&Learn 2021-1-PL01-KA220-ADU-000033465

Privacy policy

Legal basis for the processing of personal data: Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC - general data protection regulation (OJ EU L 119 of 4/05/2016, p. 1, OJ EU L 127 of 23/05/2018, p. 2 and OJ EU L 74 of 4/03/2021, page 35). hereinafter referred to as GDPR. Regulation (EU) 2016/794 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 May 2016 on the European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation (Europol), replacing and repealing Council Decisions 2009/371/JHA, 2009/934/JHA, 2009 /935/JHA, 2009/936/JHA and 2009/968/JHA (Official Journal of the European Union L 135 of 24/05/2016, p. 53). Act of 10 May 2018 (Journal of Laws 2018, item 1000)

Introduction

The following privacy policy sets out the rules for the processing and protection of your personal data in connection with the use of @ELENEconsortium websites as part of the Elders learning

I AGREE **I DISAGREE**

For the terms, conditions, and privacy policy that are described above, I have read and understand everything mentioned.

Privacy policy in selected native language

20:48 Co-funded by the European Union **SITUATED ENGLISH** Study&Learn 2021-1-PL01-KA220-ADU-000033465

Polityka Prywatności

Podstawy prawne przetwarzania danych osobowych: Rozporządzenie Parlamentu Europejskiego i Rady (UE) 2016/679 z dnia 27 kwietnia 2016 r. w sprawie ochrony osób fizycznych w związku z przetwarzaniem danych osobowych i w sprawie swobodnego przepływu takich danych oraz uchylenia dyrektywy 95/46/WE – ogólne rozporządzenie o ochronie danych (Dz. Urz. UE L 119 z 4.05.2016, str. 1, Dz. Urz. UE L 127 z 23.05.2018, str. 2 oraz Dz. Urz. UE L 74 z 4.03.2021, str. 35). dalej „RODO”. Rozporządzenie Parlamentu Europejskiego i Rady (UE) 2016/794 z dnia 11 maja 2016 r. w sprawie Agencji Unii Europejskiej ds. Współpracy Organów Ścigania (Europol), zastępującego i uchylającego decyzje Rady 2009/371/WSiSW, 2009/934/WSiSW, 2009/935/WSiSW, 2009/936/WSiSW i 2009/968/WSiSW (Dz. Urz. UE L 135 z 24.05.2016 r., s. 53). Ustawa z dnia 10 maja 2018 r. (Dz. U. 2018, poz. 1000)

Wprowadzenie

Poniższa polityka prywatności określa zasady przetwarzania i ochrony Państwa danych osobowych w związku z użytkowaniem serwisów

ZGADZAM SIĘ **NIE ZGADZAM SIĘ**

For the terms, conditions, and privacy policy that are described above, I have read and understand everything mentioned.

Privacy policy screen

The privacy policy screen is an important element of the application, informing users about how their data is used. Information about the project and EU co-financing is displayed here. The privacy policy is available in English and in translation into the user's native language, which increases the transparency of the application

BACK

SKIP

WELCOME TO THE ELENE APPAS PART OF THE
ELDERS LEARNING ENGLISH FOR EUROPE PROJECT
NO. 2021-1-PL01-KA220-ADU-000033465**Tutorial screen**

Structure of the main menu

The ELENE app's main menu is the heart of navigation, presenting six tiles with a variety of educational content such as lessons, vocabulary (memory / flash cards), instructional videos, quizzes, conversation examples and PDF materials. Each element is carefully designed to maximize the user's experience in learning English.

Lessons in the app

The section dedicated to lessons is divided into two screens - the lesson menu and the lesson screen. The user can choose the topic he wants to explore and then focus on the detailed lesson material. The design of the lessons is modern, adapted to aesthetics and comfort of use.

Thanks to the quick translation function, it is easy to see what each sentence means in the selected language in the lesson menu list. In the lesson itself there is no option for the user to become immersed in the language.

The word side of flashcards in vocabulary

The graphic side of flashcards in vocabulary

Vocabulary in the application

(Memory / Flash cards)

Vocabulary in ELENE app is presented in the form of interactive memory cards containing a word and a picture. Users can rotate the cards to better remember the word and its pronunciation, which promotes effective learning.

Video menu (similar in most categories)	The video on YouTube on Elene's channel
<p>20:11 66%</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Honorifics Transport At the airport On the plane At the hotel At the museum Passport control 	<p>20:11 65%</p> <p>THE FIRST MEETING</p> <p>Learn English with me English Conversation Practice ELENE Project</p> <p>VOCABULARY INTRODUCING YOURSELF</p> <p>Honorifics</p>

Section Video

The video section contains cards with the names of the different lessons and their corresponding images. After clicking on the card, the user is redirected to the appropriate YouTube video, which facilitates learning by observing and listening.

Selected answer on the quiz	Popup on the bottom while trying to skip the answer
Ranking unanswered	Your top answer.

Quizzes Section

Quizzes in the ELENE application allow you to check your current knowledge on selected topics. They are designed to provide a stress-free challenge, with the ability to return to previous questions and check the correctness of the answers.

Opened conversation	Conversation video	Conversation text
<p>Security officer: Next!</p> <p>Passenger: Here's my ticket.</p> <p>Security officer: Please step through the scanner.</p> <p>Passenger: (beep, beep, beep) What's wrong?</p> <p>Security officer: Please step to the side.</p> <p>Passenger: Certainly.</p> <p>Security officer: Do you have any coins in your pocket?</p> <p>Passenger: No, but I have some keys.</p> <p>Security officer: Ah, that's the problem. Put your keys in this bin and walk through the scanner again please.</p> <p>Passenger: Okay.</p> <p>Security officer: Excellent. No problem. Remember to unload your pockets before you go through security next time.</p>		<p>Security officer: Next!</p> <p>Passenger: Here's my ticket.</p> <p>Security officer: Please step through the scanner.</p> <p>Passenger: (beep, beep, beep) What's wrong?</p> <p>Security officer: Please step to the side.</p> <p>Passenger: Certainly.</p> <p>Security officer: Do you have any coins in your pocket?</p> <p>Passenger: No, but I have some keys.</p> <p>Security officer: Ah, that's the problem. Put your keys in this bin and walk through the scanner again please.</p> <p>Passenger: Okay.</p> <p>Security officer: Excellent. No problem. Remember to unload your pockets before you go through security next time.</p>

Conversation

The conversation screen has been designed to be consistent with previous ones and provide easy-to-understand dialogue that can be used in everyday situations. As in the previous screens, it also has a lesson selection menu.

PDF Materials

The PDF screen allows users to access lessons that can be downloaded, printed and used in classrooms without the need to install the application on each phone, it is divided into lessons and lesson topics are translated into the selected language.

Analysis of ELENE application statistics on Google Play

123 - 31 gru 2023

nicy, którzy odwiedzili stronę aplikacji w Sklepie

Users visit in timeline

In the analyzed period from October 17 to December 31, the ELENE application in the Google Play Store recorded a variable number of visits, with a particular point where 73 people visited the application's website in one day. The average daily visit was approximately 5 people. This data may indicate fluctuations in interest in the application, perhaps as a result of specific advertising campaigns or application updates introduced over a given period.

konwersji strony z informacjami o aplikacji ⓘ

Grupa porównawcza: Edukacja ▾

Wyświetl: Wszystkie źródła wizyt ▾

Users Conversion

Conversion, i.e. the ratio of the number of people who decided to download the application after entering the website on Google Play, was quite high - the median was 40.91%, which means that about 4 out of 10 visitors decided to download ELENE. The 25th percentile achieved a conversion value of 27.2% and the 75th percentile 55.22%, which indicates a significant number of users were convinced of the application already at the stage of familiarizing themselves with the offer. This is a very good result and indicates that the content of the application page is well matched to the expectations of potential users.

Źródło wizyt	Użytkownicy, którzy odwiedzili stronę aplikacji w Sklepie	Pozyskania ze strony z informacjami o aplikacji	Współczynnik konwersji strony z informacjami o aplikacji	Współczynnik konwersji względem aplikacji z grupy porównawczej (28 dni)	
Wybrane źródła wizyt					
▶ Wszystkie źródła wizyt w porównaniu z poprzednim okresem	321	200	62,31%	18,37%	
Inne źródła wizyt					
▶ Reklamy i odesłania w porównaniu z poprzednim okresem	205	123	60%	21,57%	
▶ Wyszukiwanie w Google Play w porównaniu z poprzednim okresem	62	48	77,42%	14,73%	
▶ Przeglądanie w Google Play w porównaniu z poprzednim okresem	54	29	53,7%	18,3%	

Visit sources and conversion efficiency

The ELENE page in the Google Play store recorded a total of 321 visits. 54 of them were the result of natural recommendations via Google Play, 62 visits resulted from searches on the platform itself, and the remaining 205 were the result of advertising activities and referrals. The total number of downloads was 200, of which 29 were natural downloads from the Google Play Store, 48 were from search, and 123 were from ads and referrals. In percentage terms, this gave an exceptionally high conversion efficiency of 62.31% from all sources.

Downloads in Google Play

Google Play introduces specific rules aimed at ensuring the reliability of information regarding the number of application downloads. The actual number of downloads may differ from the reported number, for example if the application was downloaded but never launched by the user. During the analyzed period, the application was actually downloaded a total of 145 times even if statistics of conversion says 200.

Geographic distribution

App downloads occurred primarily in Europe, with the strongest results in Portugal (45 downloads) and Poland (41 downloads). Other countries where the app has been downloaded include Slovenia (25 downloads), Turkey (24 downloads), Spain (5 downloads), Brazil and Ecuador (2 downloads each), Ireland (2 downloads) and Italy (1 download).

Analiza zmian

 Uwzględnij wybrane: Kraje/regiony

Kraje/regiony o największej zmianie między pierwszym przedziałem czasu w wybranym okresie a ostatnim przedziałem z pełnymi danymi

Liczba instalacji

■ Liczba instalacji (Wszystkie urządzenia, Unikalne urządzenia, Z odcinków czasu, Dzień)

Podsumowanie

5.000 ★

Domyślna ocena w Google Play

5.000 ★

Średnia ocena od początku

21

Użytkownicy

Users and app rating

The number of active users who regularly use the ELENE application is 21. The application received a maximum average rating of 5.00, which is rare in the Google Play store, and additionally received 13 positive reviews, which proves the great satisfaction of those who decided to rate ELENE

User comments

Based on examples of reviews from Play Store users, the ELENE application is positively received by people who want to practically apply the acquired knowledge. Comments indicate great satisfaction with educational videos and tests checking learning progress. Users appreciate the ability to learn with videos and the application is also targeted at older users, which confirms its universality and usefulness.

- | | |
|---|---|
|
Marek M
★★★★★ 15 listopada 2023
Great app to learn language with practical usage of words and expressions in real situations. Many videos explaining what when and why to say, vocabulary page, and test to check your progress. Great app, hope it will develop further!
Czy to było pomocne? <input type="button" value="Tak"/> <input type="button" value="Nie"/> |
Agnieszka Chęcińska
★★★★★ 21 października 2023
ELENE APP has improved my language skills and made my life easier, Thank you for supporting elders! Agnieszka
3 osoby uznały tę opinię za przydatną
Czy to było pomocne? <input type="button" value="Tak"/> <input type="button" value="Nie"/> |
|
Elżbieta Sokolowska
★★★★★ 15 listopada 2023
Świetna aplikacja. Myślę, że wielu Seniorów z niej skorzysta.
Czy to było pomocne? <input type="button" value="Tak"/> <input type="button" value="Nie"/> |
Molipow
★★★★★ 14 listopada 2023
jest ok
Czy to było pomocne? <input type="button" value="Tak"/> <input type="button" value="Nie"/> |
|
Neko Chan
★★★★★ 15 listopada 2023
Nauka z filmami jest bardziej efektywna. Super
Czy to było pomocne? <input type="button" value="Tak"/> <input type="button" value="Nie"/> |
Ewa Fajer
★★★★★ 15 listopada 2023
Bardzo dobra apka
Czy to było pomocne? <input type="button" value="Tak"/> <input type="button" value="Nie"/> |

Summary of statistics

Analysis of the download statistics of the ELENE application in Google Play allows us to outline its presence on the educational applications market and the effectiveness of marketing activities. Downloads and conversions show positive trends with some high scores, especially in conversions, where almost half of people visiting the app's page decided to download it. The actual number of application activations after downloading, although it could be higher, still confirms that the application has a stable group of users. The multitude of positive reviews and the maximum average rating indicate user satisfaction, which is crucial for app recommendation.

ELENE app summary

The application enables effective learning of English, using effective teaching methods and innovative technologies. Its interface is user-friendly and intuitive, which promotes involvement in the educational process and facilitates access to rich educational resources. By personalizing experiences, interactive learning methods and adapting to different age groups, the application meets the expectations of a wide range of users. Features such as Quick Translate, the availability of materials in various formats (PDF, videos, quizzes) and dialogues along with the transcription of its content from a YouTube video distinguish ELENE from other educational applications. The success of the application measured by high user ratings and their mature opinions confirms the value offered by the ELENE application.

ELENE APP

Tutorials for the elene application in partner languages

- In Polish – <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0wus8S2X7Rc>
- In Spanish – <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ju4kkH-o8uo>
- In Portuguese – <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Bkvh9SYhg6s>
- In Turkish – <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=c7jR0APXQak>
- In Slovenian – <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5zwTv6odBf8>
- In English – <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2kS813rRL9Y>